

THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES OF EFFECTIVE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

This article emphasizes that effective classroom management is a vital part of teaching. A classroom that is well-managed creates an environment where students can learn and grow effectively. However, managing a classroom can be particularly challenging, especially for new teachers. Classroom management can be approached in different ways, and what works for one teacher may not work for another. Despite this, there are certain universal principles that can help all educators enhance their classroom management skills.

Key words: aid, online, activity, strength, weakness, enhance, interactively, skill,

learner, prediction, material, Rapport, TTT vs. STT, Seating & interaction, Monitoring, Instructions, Board work.

Setting clear expectations for students is the first step towards good classroom management. Establish clear expectations for social interactions, intellectual pursuits, and academic performance. Students should be made aware of these expectations at the start of the school year, and they should be discussed and readjusted frequently.

Key Principles of Good Classroom Management, including:

1. Rapport

- Rapport refers to the understanding and relationship between a teacher and their students. It involves showing empathy when students express their feelings and experiences. Teachers can build rapport by learning every student's name, maintaining eye contact, designing high-quality lessons, engaging learners, and consistently smiling. Establishing good rapport can lead to more effective and successful teaching.

2. Teacher Talking Time (TTT) vs. Student Talking Time (STT)

- In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and English Language Teaching (ELT) contexts, terms like Teacher Talking Time (TTT) and Student Talking Time (STT) are commonly used. STT is essential as it allows students to practice new language skills they have learned and to review and recycle existing language. It also enables students to combine and blend previously learned language with

new vocabulary or structural elements. Traditionally, TTT was central to teaching, but current approaches place much more emphasis on STT.

3. Seating and Interaction

- The arrangement of seating in a classroom is as important as the curriculum, instructional strategies, and differentiated instruction. The way students are seated can affect their learning outcomes. Reorganizing the classroom to fit different teaching methods is essential. The best classroom seating arrangements depend on factors such as the size and shape of the room, the students' age range, potential distractions, teaching methods, and learning objectives. The arrangement of seats can significantly improve students' performance, and student-centered seating is now more common. In online classes, managing when students speak and careful consideration of seating are important.

4. Monitoring

- Monitoring involves a series of tasks that teachers perform to track learners' performance in class. The main purposes are to inform instructional choices and provide feedback to students. Monitoring occurs when a teacher actively listens and observes as students engage in activities. Teachers monitor for various reasons and in different ways, depending on the objective of the activity. Monitoring student performance helps collect useful information to track their progress. It also helps identify students who need assistance, allowing the teacher to take necessary actions to support them. Teachers should watch over group discussions, pair projects, and team activities, walking around to ensure students stay on task and employing control strategies if they are not.

5. Instructions

- Clear instructions are crucial for classroom activities. Teachers need to ensure that students understand instructions to participate in language learning activities effectively. Giving clear instructions involves using simple English and engaging students in communicative learning tasks. Instructions should be given step-by-step, with modeling strategies if necessary, to make them clear. Writing complicated instructions on the board can support learners. Teachers should practice effective teacher talk to achieve clear instructions, emphasizing simplicity.

6. Board Work

- The classroom board, whether physical or virtual, is a key component in enhancing the teaching and learning process. Students need an accurate written record of new topics, and the board plays a crucial role. Teachers use the board

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to present new language, record vocabulary, brainstorm ideas, write keywords, encourage interaction, and play interactive games. Virtual boards in online classes can replicate these functions, using collaborative tools like Zoom's whiteboard, inserting emojis, and engaging students in interactive activities to enhance their learning performance.

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